

Profile-Driven Banded Smith-Waterman acceleration for Short Read Alignment

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Abstract—Short read alignment is a critical step in genomic pipelines that requires optimization due to the enormous input size and complexity of SmithWaterman string matching. Several optimization techniques have been examined, such as hardware acceleration, heuristics and pre-filtering. This work combines these approaches into a single powerful solution that leverages the low edit rate of reads and the principles of Banded SmithWaterman, to highlight the value of creating accelerators customized to the input accuracy requirements. We propose a dataset-specific multi-dataflow design that leverages both pre-filtering and Banded SmithWaterman to meet the demands of the datasets in both throughput and accuracy.

Index Terms—Short Read Alignment, Reconfigurable Acceleration, Dataflow Computing, Smith Waterman, Profiling

I. INTRODUCTION

Genomics is a fast-evolving research domain, that allows scientists to understand the mechanisms responsible for the genetic diversity. The growth in the field has been facilitated by advances in sequencing technologies, that have brought about the generation of billions of short fragments of DNA at low cost and increased quality, with error rates as low as 0.01% [1]. The nucleotide short *reads* generated by sequencing platforms are utilized to reconstruct the sample genome and compare it to the reference genome as part of various analyses such as variant calling and epigenetics [2]. This reconstruction is achieved through *short read alignment*, that maps the short reads to a location in the reference genome that is most likely its origin. Most aligners [3]–[5] adopt a *seed-and-extend* strategy to find possible matches of the read on the reference genome. *Seeding* fragments each read into even shorter pieces called *seeds* that align exactly on the reference genome and creates a pool of candidates for valid alignments. In the *seed extension*, each seed is extended into a gapped alignment, i.e. allowing mismatches or *edits*.

In modern aligners, the extension step is most frequently implemented based on Smith-Waterman [6] dynamic programming algorithm for string matching that operates in two stages. Matrix Fill fills a similarity score matrix between a read and reference sequence. The fewer the gaps and mismatches between the sequences, the higher the score of each alignment is and therefore the similarity of the two sequences. Traceback stage starts from the cell in the similarity matrix with the highest score, and traverses the matrix backwards until it

reaches a zero-score cell, i.e. the first match point of the two sequences. During backtracing, it identifies all potential edits and thus reconstructs the alignment path. The excessive time requirements and computational intensity of this step however forms a major bottleneck and the need for optimization is imperative. As mentioned in [7], performance optimization efforts follow two different approaches: i) the first one targets optimization of a single alignment task [8], [9], whereas ii) the alternative focus on decreasing the volume of alignment tasks [10].

Hardware acceleration of alignment tasks: The first category can be further distinguished into solutions that leverage hardware acceleration and solutions that employ heuristic techniques or a combination of the two. Hardware accelerations for SmithWaterman have been developed for a variety of devices such as GPUs, ASICs and FPGAs. Due to their bit-level customization capabilities, FPGAs have emerged as promising Smith-Waterman accelerators both for industry [11] and academia [9], [12]. Most of them, [8], [13] are based on a wavefront approach that implements a pipeline of PEs as a systolic array. The majority of them focus on providing a highly optimized accelerator for the first stage, however they do not provide a Traceback implementation, which excludes them from integration into commonly-used software aligners. Edlib [14] software aligner implements the alignment by using vectorized operations and replacing SmithWaterman with a simpler algorithm that calculates the Levehnstein distance instead. Other software aligners rely mainly on heuristic techniques to improve performance. For example, Bowtie2 [5] utilizes a heuristic of SmithWaterman that ignores selected dependencies in order to leverage SIMD instructions and adds a correction step to account for any errors. Another common heuristic is Banded SmithWaterman [15], which only looks for alignments that adhere to an edit threshold, i.e. around the diagonal of the matrix. Recent works target Banded SmithWaterman for accelerating either long reads alignment [16] or sequencing datasets of high sequencing error rates [17].

Seed-extension pre-filtering: The second category is represented by pre-filtering algorithms that aim at decreasing the vast amount of seed extension tasks, by discarding candidate alignments based on a predefined threshold for the edit distance. Several pre-filtering algorithms [10], [18], [19] have now been developed that have noted significant improvement in accuracy and performance since early efforts. SneakySnake [10] is a state-of-the-art pre-filtering algorithm, as it achieves

higher accuracy alignment results through a highly efficient decision technique to discard unnecessary extensions.

Despite the promising results on genomics efficiency, the above research categories are still evolving in isolation, thus limiting the potential gains of a cooperative optimization approach. This is attributed to the fundamentally different scope of each category. On one hand, *genomic hardware acceleration* is driven by *data-agnostic* decisions that built accelerators able to perform accurate seed extension on generic datasets. On the other hand, *pre-filtering optimization* is a fully *data-aware* procedure that delivers best results when customized to the underlying dataset.

In this paper, we bridge hardware acceleration and pre-filtering for alignment optimization by introducing a profile-driven Smith-Waterman accelerator design. We leverage the edit profile of genomic datasets to pinpoint dominant edit thresholds in the alignments and exploit them to configure different Banded SmithWaterman accelerators. The adoption of these profile-driven upper limits and resource-efficient Banded SmithWaterman accelerators enables the provision of a highly parallel Banded Smith-Waterman accelerated system. We design an heterogeneous system, with different accelerators supporting the full range of edit thresholds and employ a pre-filtering algorithm to guide candidate alignments to an accelerator that supports the expected edit threshold, thus delivering a high throughput alignment system without compromising accuracy.

Our main innovations are summarized as follows: (i) we introduce a profile-driven design methodology leveraging Banded Smith-Waterman for seed-extension acceleration customized to the input edit threshold distribution (ii) we design and deliver a highly optimized dataflow implementation for Banded Smith-Waterman seed-extension targeting FPGA devices and (iii) we implement a dataset-specific multi-dataflow system that significantly accelerates pre-filtering seed-extension alignment with negligible accuracy loss. Through an extensive experimental campaign, we evaluate the efficiency of both the newly introduced Banded Smith-Waterman accelerator as well as the delivered profile-driven multi-dataflow system against a rich set of state-of-the-art alignment solutions. The evaluation shows that the proposed Banded Smith-Waterman accelerator delivers a $\times 34$ speedup over state-of-the-art software aligner and $\times 1.53$ over state-of-the-art dataflow SmithWaterman accelerator [12] and $\times 3$ over GACT RTL accelerator [9]. Moreover, the proposed multi-dataflow system delivers average speedups of $\times 1.8$ over state-of-the-art multi-accelerator FPGA solutions [12] that employ generic and input-agnostic accelerators, further validating the efficiency of the proposed profile-driven approach for accelerators' parallelism customization.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: we first motivate and sketch the basic concepts of the proposed profile-driven customization methodology in Section II. In Section III, we design and detail the micro-architectural decisions of the introduced multi-dataflow accelerated system. Section IV provides a thorough and in-depth evaluation and comparative

Fig. 1: Distribution of number of edits for alignments for three different datasets.

analysis of the proposed solution w.r.t. state-of-the-art.

II. PROFILE-DRIVEN GENOMIC ARCHITECTURE OPTIMIZATION

In this work, we propose to leverage the edit profile of modern short read datasets in order to create a high-throughput accelerated system fit to the accuracy needs of the input.

Profiling insights: In order to evaluate the impact of the edit profile on the architecture, we meticulously study the behavior and results during alignment of three different input datasets: (i) a simulated dataset of 60 million 100-base long reads created by NEAT [20] simulator, (ii) 60 million reads of often-used sample NA12878 (ERR194147_1) provided by 1000 Genomes Project Release3 [21] and (iii) CLL, a real-patient dataset assembled as part of research for Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia. Fig.1 presents a histogram of the number of edits for all alignments found for each dataset. The selected edit thresholds in the histograms, i.e. 2, 5, 10, 18, 30 edits, correspond to critical values for which a significant increase in the number of aligned reads occurs. For the simulated dataset, 70.8% of the examined alignments include at most a single edit. The same percentage is equal to 74.4% and 82% for the NA12878 and CLL dataset. The number of reads that align for a given edit threshold, increases rapidly (by 5-10%) for threshold ranging from 1 to 8. However, for values greater than 10 the incremental changes is in the order of 0.01%. In fact, for all datasets the 99.99% of alignments contain fewer than 18 edits.

Banded Smith-Waterman: The first valuable insight of the profiling is the potential impact of the low edit number on the accelerator architecture. Fig.2 illustrates the placement of an exact as well as a gapped alignment on the score matrix. Both alignments start from the seed hit, i.e. the first match point, however the gapped alignment deviates from the *seed diagonal* as it includes an edit. The smaller the edit distance, the narrower the band of the matrix that the alignment spans. This is by definition exploited by Banded Smith-Waterman [15], that is based on the observation that the max score in the matrix appears around the seed diagonal at a maximum distance equal to the number of edits. Therefore, for a given edit threshold, Banded Smith-Waterman focuses on the respective band within the matrix and eliminates the need for storing and searching the entire score matrices. Fig.2 demonstrates the band of interest within the complete matrix, after taking the *edit threshold* into consideration. The final alignment will be found within the area marked by the seed diagonal, the *edit threshold* upper seed diagonals

Fig. 2: Banded SmithWaterman example for *edit threshold* 2.

and the *edit threshold* lower seed diagonals. As Traceback also checks the neighboring cells forming the *halo* area of Fig.2, the band of interest has *band_length* equal to $2 * \text{edit_threshold} + 3$. Thus, studying the edit profile of the input dataset can help us avoid overprovisioning of resources and design more resource efficient seed-extension accelerators.

Profile-driven genomic accelerator architecture optimization: The second important insight does not concern the low edit threshold itself but rather the frequency in which each threshold occurs. The distribution per edit threshold straightforwardly translates into a similar distribution of the time taken up by each type of alignment, i.e. alignments with 0-1 edits take up at least 70% of the total dataset alignment time. This heterogeneity suggests that the overall performance could benefit more if we instantiated multiple smaller-sized accelerators and assigned them to the corresponding alignment types in a similar distribution.

Let us assume K generic parallel accelerators that take up the acceleration of the alignment of a given dataset. We claim that there is a configuration of k_1, k_2, \dots, k_l edit-customized accelerators that 1) follow the edit distribution of the dataset and 2) satisfy the inequality $\sum_{i=1}^l k_i > K$, so that they achieve a greater overall speedup than K for equal resources utilization. Let us assume a realistic scenario with an edit threshold distribution 70-20-10% for corresponding thresholds of 1, 5, 15 edits, respectively. We also assume Banded SW accelerators i) with area occupation equal to a fraction of the area of the single general accelerator, proportional to their band size, and ii) with equal execution latencies for all band sizes, e.g. $1.5\times$ faster than the software. Under the above assumptions, Fig.3 depicts exploration results for differ-

Fig. 3: Example of applying generic accelerators as opposed to employing smaller accelerators fit to the input edit profile.

Fig. 4: Overview of profile-driven acceleration strategy and system architecture for a distribution of 60-20-10-10%.

ent K, k_1, k_2, k_3 accelerator allocations, in terms of latency and resources utilization. As shown, configuration points of k_1, k_2, k_3 fluctuate lower than the corresponding K points for the same resource utilization percentage. For example, $K = 4$ generic accelerators take up 45% of hardware resources and achieve a speedup of $\times 4.5$, where $k_1, k_2, k_3 = 6, 2, 1$ customized accelerators take up as much hardware resources for a speedup of $\times 12.8$.

We leverage the above insights to create a system with multiple dataflow accelerators, i.e. multi-dataflow system, customized to the dataset specifications in terms of edit threshold. As shown in Fig.4 this can be achieved by first profiling the input dataset to extract the edit distribution and pinpoint the edit thresholds for which there is a spike in the number of aligned reads. The number of thresholds indicates the number of different types of edit-customized Banded Smith-Waterman accelerators. Each type can support up to a predefined number of edits, equal to the found thresholds. The number of accelerators allocated for each type follows the same distribution as the edit thresholds. Then during runtime, SneakySnake [10] pre-filtering algorithm classifies input candidate alignments into the respective edit threshold category and assigns each alignment to the corresponding accelerator.

III. DESIGN OF DATAFLOW GENOMIC ACCELERATOR

The proposed multi-dataflow design includes multiple single Banded Smith-Waterman accelerators, which have been developed utilizing dataflow computing. Each one is configured with an edit threshold selected at profiling based on the proposed methodology. The single Banded Smith-Waterman accelerator includes two computing units, one for each of SmithWaterman stages, i.e. Matrix-Fill and Traceback. Matrix Fill receives read-reference pairs as alignment candidates and computes the matrices E,F,H. Once the matrices are ready, they are traversed in reverse order by Traceback to identify edits. At any time, they execute in parallel and in pipeline manner, i.e. as Matrix Fill operates on an alignment pair, Traceback processes the matrices created for the previous pair.

Matrix Fill Banded Design: Fig.2 illustrates the dependencies and parallelism of Banded Smith-Waterman. The computation of matrices E,F,H by Matrix Fill is characterized by anti-diagonal dependencies, as each cell value depends on the left, up and diagonal neighbours. All cells within the same antidiagonal can be computed in parallel forming a wavefront. A parallel Matrix Fill implementation is based on this wavefront approach to fill the matrices. Banded Matrix

Fig. 5: PE computation of score matrices and BRAM allocation of band elements.

Fill is implemented as a typical systolic array architecture of Processing Elements (PEs) equal in number to the length of the read sequence. Each PE is responsible for computing a single row of the matrix in Fig.2. All PEs operate in parallel and compute all cells within the same antidiagonal per wavefront. As a result, the computed cells should be stored per antidiagonal rather than per row. Fig.5 depicts the PE array computations and the matrix required to store all antidiagonals. Each row in this matrix corresponds to a row of the original matrix and each column to an antidiagonal. Each one includes as many elements as the length of the longest antidiagonal, i.e. the read length.

Storing Optimization Scheme: Fig.5 also illustrates how the *band* elements are stored in a smaller matrix. PEs temporarily store each anti-diagonal in a read-length vector. Each antidiagonal includes at most $bandLength/2 + 1$ cells that belong to the banded area. Therefore we need to allocate a matrix of vectors, i.e. *bandVectors*, of length $bandLength/2 + 1$ rather than $bandLength$ to store all band cells. A mask of length $bandLength/2 + 1$ shifts through the read-length vector written by the PEs, selects the band cells and stores them in memory. Note that storing the *bandRow* vectors in a BRAM changes the relative position of some neighbor cells by an offset of 1.

Traceback Banded Design: Traceback receives these *bandVectors* in reverse order and constructs the alignment path by keeping track of the first and last matching characters of the sequences and all potential edits in between. Fig.6 illustrates an abstract diagram of the logic implemented by Traceback. Traceback encodes each backward step in the alignment as one of the available distinct states: i) initial state ii) H-up, iii) H-left, iv) F-up, v) E-left, vi) H-diagonal, vi) *waiting* state and vii) *finished* state. In order to enable Traceback to decide its next state, i.e. the next hop of the backward path, we check all possible origins from neighboring cells in the two subsequent antidiagonals. These checks are taking place in parallel and result in setting a single bit of an 8-bit vector, i.e. one bit allocated for each possible state. This

Fig. 6: Logic Diagram of Traceback Dataflow implementation.

8-bit vector then is leveraged as a selector signal in a set of parallel one-hot-multiplexers. Each one-hot-multiplexer links to each one of the internal Traceback variables, which actually define the Traceback's state space. Thus, the selector signal is utilized to update all identifiers of the next state such as the type of cell (E,F or H), the index within the read/reference sequence and the index within the *bandRow* vector.

Special attention is required with indexing when accessing the neighboring cells within the two subsequent vectors, as *bandRow* vectors have been shifted to be stored in BRAM. Since the two subsequent vectors are shifted by one position at most, we add a correction offset of value 1 when necessary.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Experimental Setup

The experimental setup includes a dual socket Intel Xeon Gold 6138 (2.0GHz, 14nm) with 128GB DDR4 DRAM (2133MHz) that is connected through PCIe 2.0 with Maxeler's MAX5C platform. The specific MAX5C provides two MAX5 dataflow engines, i.e. two Xilinx VU9P Ultrascale FPGAs. Accelerators have been developed using MaxJ dataflow language [22] and compiled with MaxCompiler 2018.3 that invokes Vivado 2017.4 for place and route purposes.

B. Banded Smith-Waterman Evaluation

1) *Accuracy Evaluation:* The adoption of Banded Smith-Waterman reduces the accuracy of the alignment by default, as it eradicates alignments that do not meet the edit threshold. This section evaluates the accuracy of short read alignment when applying pre-filtering and leveraging the proposed Banded SmithWaterman implementation for the respective edit threshold. As a reference, we utilize the results of Bowtie2 aligner. Bowtie2 aligner by default considers 150 as a maximum limit for number of edits, which is equivalent to a no-limit alignment strategy for the 100-base length of the given datasets. Pre-filtering is implemented by SneakySnake, that discards all candidates with more edits than the specified edit threshold. We consider edit thresholds that vary from 1 up to almost 20% of the read length of 100. We evaluate the accuracy on the three datasets described in Section II. The comparison is illustrated in Fig.7. The results are in accordance with the edit distribution findings, as for most datasets the alignment rate converges to the optimal one for

Fig. 7: Alignment success when using SneakySnake pre-filtering and the proposed Banded Smith-Waterman accelerator for seed extension.

an edit threshold greater than 10, which includes most of the alignments.

2) *Performance Evaluation*: The performance of the proposed accelerator is compared against both software and hardware state-of-the-art alignment implementations. The comparison is based on the throughput of all implementations, i.e. the number of computed alignments per seconds. We first consider a single-instance comparison strategy, which employs a single thread for the software aligners and a single acceleration instance for the proposed aligner. We utilize the following state-of-the-art software aligners: (i) Edlib [14], a C/C++ aligner that implements exact sequence alignment using the Levehnstein edit distance for seed extension, (ii) WFA [23], a software aligner that performs exact alignment based on a gap-affine scoring scheme and optimized with the wavefront parallelism approach, (iii) KSW2 [24], a C library that aligns pairs of biological sequences based on dynamic programming, (iv) the vectorized SSE2-based Smith-Waterman implementation utilized in Bowtie2 that adopts a heuristic to support vectorization with 8 SIMD lanes [5], (v) the open-source software implementation of GenASM [25], an approximate string matching acceleration framework for genome sequence analysis. The single-instance proposed Banded SmithWaterman accelerator includes an 100-PE array and is built with a clock frequency of 400MHz. Since edit threshold only affects the resource utilization of the single-instance design, all edit threshold designs can be utilized to measure the performance. We utilize the Simulated dataset of 100-base long reads for execution. The results are found in Fig.8. The proposed Banded design acquires a speedup of $\times 34$ over the fastest software implementation, which is Edlib.

We also compare our design with two state-of-the-art hardware accelerators, GACT [9] and GANDAFL [12]. GACT accelerator is part of Darwin short read aligner and implements an RTL PE-based design of SmithWaterman MatrixFill and Traceback. We utilize the open-source implementation of GACT and implement the hardware using Vivado HLS 2018.3. We developed an in-house implementation of GANDAFL, which is a dataflow MatrixFill and Traceback FPGA implementation that also targets Maxeler MAX5C workstation. We utilize MaxCompiler 2018.3 for development and synthesis purposes. We examine two different scenarios for a rounded comparison. The first one compares the throughput of a single instance of each accelerator, to evaluate the capability of

Fig. 8: Throughput comparison between Proposed Banded 10-edit threshold accelerator and state-of-the-art SW aligners.

TABLE I: Hardware Accelerators Configurations for throughput comparison.

Accelerator	Configuration		Utilization			Clock (MHz)
	Instances	PEs	BRAM18	DSP	Logic	
GACT	1	128	3.10%	0.0%	2.39%	250
	25	128	77.55%	0.0%	60.71%	150
GANDAFL	1	100	24.75%	0.10%	8.68%	200
	3	100	65.53%	0.31%	22.62%	200
Proposed	1	100	11.78%	0.10%	7.60%	400
	18 edits	8	53.94%	1.4%	55.44%	250

the design to deliver a single alignment result faster than state-of-the-art solutions. The second one compares multi-accelerator designs that leverage the maximum capacity of the same target FPGA device. We utilize the FPGA included within MAX5C platform, i.e. Xilinx VU9P and assume that all designs share the same PCIe connection. Table I summarizes the optimal configurations (that minimize the Area \times Delay product metric) selected for each accelerator for the examined scenarios. As seen in Fig.9, the Proposed Banded implementation achieves a $\times 1.53$ speedup over GANDAFL dataflow and a $\times 3$ speedup over GACT single instance designs. Thanks to efficient resource utilization, the proposed multi-dataflow design fits 8 accelerators on the FPGA and achieves a $\times 4.77$ speedup over the 3-dataflow instances of GANDAFL accelerator. The dataflow computing model and efficient resource utilization secure a $\times 26.35$ speedup over a 12-instance design of GACT.

C. Multi-Dataflow System Evaluation

Based on the proposed methodology, we evaluate the performance of customized accelerated systems on the Simulated, NA12878 and CLL datasets. First we leverage the edit profiles and build the respective multi-dataflow designs for a clock of 250MHz. Table II summarizes the configurations and the percentage of alignments covered within each threshold selected. We compare these designs with our GANDAFL in-house implementation that includes 3 accelerator instances that allow up to 17 edits and is clocked at 200MHz. Both designs are also compared with Bowtie2 aligner, which generates the input alignments and serves as a reference for the alignment rate. SneakySnake pre-filtering has been leveraged to classify the candidate alignments and assign them to the respective dataflow accelerator based on the edit threshold. As seen in Fig.10, the proposed approach delivers a speedup up to $\times 440$ over Bowtie2 aligner and $\times 1.8$ over GANDAFL conventional accelerated approach. Note that this speedup does not come

Fig. 9: Throughput and Resource utilization efficiency evaluation for HW Smith-Waterman accelerators.

TABLE II: Multi-Dataflow Configurations customized to the edit profiles of input datasets.

Dataset	Configuration		
	Edit threshold	Instances	Alignments covered
Simulated	1-2-10-18	5-1-1-1	70.8-81.4-99.7-99.9%
NA127828	1-2-5-18	5-1-1-1	74.4-87.3-99.6-99.9%
CLL	1-5-18	6-1-1	82.5-93.51-99.9%

Fig. 10: Performance and accuracy evaluation of proposed customized accelerated system.

at the expense of alignment rate as the alignment rate has converged to the reference one for the selected thresholds.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we employ hardware acceleration and pre-filtering methods to present a profile-driven Smith-Waterman accelerated design for short read alignment. Extensive profiling of genomic datasets reveals low edit thresholds that can be leveraged by Banded SmithWaterman to create resource-efficient accelerators that are customized to the edit profile of the input. The accelerated system is configured with multiple Banded accelerators covering a full range of edits to achieve both high throughput as well as high accuracy alignment. Experimental evaluation shows that the proposed system outperforms state-of-the-art solutions by $\times 1.8$.

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